

Constraints Faced by Small and Medium Enterprises in Raising Funds for Financing

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Srinidhi, P., and

B. KhaviPriya.

“Constraints Faced by Small and Medium Enterprises in Raising Funds for Financing.”

Shanlax International Journal of Commerce, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 207–11.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412606>

P.Srinidhi & B.KhaviPriya

M Com Accounting and Finance IIInd year

*ShrimathiDevkunvarNanalal Bhatt Vaishnav College for Women
Chennai, Tamil Nadu.*

Abstract

SME's are playing a vital role in economic development and also for the growth of India's economic growth. SME's contribution to Indian economy development is at large. According to Micro Small and Medium Enterprise (MSME) Act 2006 in India, considers investment rationing for both the manufacturing sectors and the service sectors. Government of India have introduced many industrial estates, industrial parks, special economic zones for enhancing SME's status. With the onset of the globalization process, SMEs are lagging behind the rival firms. Those firms originate from the neighboring countries in terms of export competitiveness.

This study will help to identify the challenges faced by SME's about lack of finance, lack of infrastructure, lack of networking, lack of information, lack of production facilities, lack of marketing skills and many more.

Keywords: Economic growth, credit facilities, risk, and uncertainty, SME, Finance.

Introduction

The term SMEs may be defined asunder

- Small – SMEs are small either in terms of the number of employees - 10 persons for ‘small’ to 200 persons for ‘medium’ depending on the country’s laws, and with limited working capital and assets, and the overall turnover of the enterprise is small, compared to larger businesses.
- Single–Most SMEs are owner-managed businesses. Any enterprise with 250 to 500 employees as the limit is termed as an SME. The term ‘single’ also refers to single products produced or services provided.
- Local–SMEs are primarily local as their market is usually localized to the area where they are located (same city, district or state), and to that, they operate from a place of residence called Small Office Home Office (SOHO)

Statistics

1. No of SMEs in India: Both registered and unregistered sums up to 4.25 crores.
2. Percentage in the total industry: 95%
3. GDP contribution- manufacturing sector: 6.11%

4. GDP contribution- service sector: 24.63%
5. Export contribution: 40% of total exports.
6. Bank lending: 16% of total bank lending.

Source: Annual Reports of Ministry of MSME

Development of SMEs

Early 90s Middle-class people were engaged in the “working class” by themselves in Government or PSU jobs instead of getting out and build something for their own. Some socio-economic factors affected start-ups.

At this time, many the IT (Information Technology) companies were boosted up and increased the demand for fund flow and thereby reducing the manual work.

More people were leaving their corporate jobs to either return to their family business or to start on their own business with their creative ideas. It had an impact on the employee’s retention rate in the corporate sector. This factor boosted the growth of SMEs.

Role of SMEs

- For a developing country like India, SMEs contribution becomes vital for bridging the gap between the rich and poor.
- They act as a powerhouse for creating a number of employment opportunities demanding comparatively less capital investment.
- It nurtures the local economies through growth and innovations.
- Industrializing the rural and backward areas by uplifting and moving them towards progressive state condition; in turn, thereby reducing the gap of income across different regions, and bringing in the balance in the income of people across the country.
- A push for big corporates to invest in the country and thereby increasing the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of nation, which is one of the key indicators of economic development.
- Contributing massively to the socio-economic growth of India. Thus, reducing the Poverty, Inequality, and Unemployment contributes to the development of the country’s economy.
- SME’s also contribute to the promotion of balanced economic development.

Fiscal Expenditure	2018-2019	2019-2020
Total Expenditure	Rs 24,57,235 Cr	Rs 27,84,200 Cr
Income Support to Farmers	Rs 20,000 Cr	Rs 75,000 Cr
Capital Expenditures	Rs 1,50,000 Cr	Rs 3,36,292 Cr
Centrally Sponsored Schemes	Rs 3,27,679 Cr	Rs 3,04,849 Cr
National Education	Rs 38,572 Cr	Rs 32,334 Cr
Integrated Child Development Scheme	Rs 27,584 Cr	Rs 23,357 Cr
Scheduled Castes Welfare	Rs 76,801 Cr	Rs 56,619 Cr
Scheduled Tribe Welfare	Rs 50,086 Cr	Rs 39,135 Cr

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the turnover earned by SMEs.
- To examine and analyze the issues faced by Indian SMEs in raising funds.
- To provide solutions to overcome the problems faced by SMEs in raising finance.

Research Questions

- What do you see as the key limiting factor or constraint to get enhanced finance from various sources?
- What was the annual turnover of your firm during the financial year 2018?
- Among various sources of financing, which of the following sources have been used by your firm?

Analysis

Reasons for Poor Smes Credit	Total Number of Response	Percentage
Lack of Experience	4	10
Poor Financials of Enterprises	24	60
No Collaterals	2	5
Lack of Infrastructure Facilities	4	10
Low Managerial Skills	4	10
Others	2	5

	Total number of response
Bank loan	8
Retained earnings	12
Friends and family	4
Equity funding	0
Trade credit	0
Capital subsidy	0
NBFCs	6
Factoring Leasing or Hiring	10

Turnover (In Lakhs)	Total Number of Response
100-500	0
500-1000	8
1000-3000	14
3000-5000	16
5000 and Above	2

Suggestions to the Problems Faced by the SMEs in Raising Funds

Here is the list of problems faced by the Indian SMEs in raising their funds for the requirements

1. Inadequate collateral securities.
2. Lower technical and management skills.
3. Competition from large enterprises.
4. Inadequate capacity to afford long term financing.
5. Entrepreneur’s financial literacy.
6. Personal credit is linked or correlated with business credit.
7. No venture capital.
8. Depends on supplier’s credit, factoring and discounting.
9. Lower concentration on working capital and poor working capital management.
10. Ambiguous project.

• Inadequate Collateral Securities

The SMEs process less number of assets, which is insufficient to pledge for raising funds. Financial organizations demand collateral securities, which are not sufficient in the hands of SMEs. Thus it becomes a major drawback for them to raise funds.

- **Low level of technical skills**

Entrepreneurs were not equipped with the technical skills, and they are unaware of technology used in raising funds, which becomes a drawback for them to access real-time process.

- **Competition from large enterprises**

SMEs face the competition from the large enterprises as they lack popularity in the market. Every distinct person would not be aware of the SMEs; rather; they would concentrate on more branded and well-known enterprises.

- **Inadequate capacity to afford long term financing**

The sources of long term finance are capital market, bank loans, leasing, and retained earnings. SMEs suffer to their inability to secure long term financing even in such markets. SMEs rely upon the organized financing techniques, for example, family, friends, customer advances.

- **Entrepreneur's financial literacy**

Indian entrepreneurs lack financial literacy as they are unaware of the available financial instruments to raise funds in the enterprise. Socio-economic factors act as a hindrance to expand and adopt the new updates in the financial world.

- **Personal credits werelinked with business credit**

Personal credit history will factor heavily in the approval and in determining the amount of credit extended to entrepreneurs. The Credit scores are mostly used by lenders to decide regarding a loan application or even a credit card. A Credit score of the entrepreneur determines if he can avail the loan or not. A poor credit score can mean that his loan application is rejected and he would have to look elsewhere to raise finance. A credit score is used to determine the rate of interest offered by financial institutions. He may get a loan, but if his credit score is not good, he will be considered risky, and his interest rate would be higher.

- **Ambiguous project**

The lending institutions assess the cost and risk of lending based on several factors, which is why; the eligibility criteria for individual business loan products differ. The lenders evaluate the business proposals or projects submitted by the borrower based on numerous key factors. But they do not follow predefined rules or pre-set standards for project appraisal. The lack of standards makes it challenging for lenders to evaluate business plans and, borrowers to prepare business plans.

On the whole, the latest financial technologies help lending institutions to address common challenges in SME lending. But the entrepreneurs must be financially literate and adopt the latest technologies to access credit without any hassle and delay. Hence, both lenders and borrowers have to resolve any issues to become a part of the growing SME lending market.

References

1. Pearson. Strategic thinking, New York, Prentice Hall.
2. Torre., Soledad., Schmukler., Bank involvement with SMEs: beyond relationship lending.
3. Zavatta., Financing technology entrepreneurs & SMEs in developing countries: challenges opportunities.
4. Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises, Annual report.